

NORMAL AND PATHOLOGICAL PHYSIOLOGY

INVISIBLE CLOCK CAN AFFECT AWAKENING: EXPERIMENTS

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Abstract

A phenomenon has been discovered indicating that a person can awaken from sleep one or several times a night at some of precise time points, as displayed on a clock that is hidden from sight. These time points reflect the 0-, 15-, 30-, and 45-minute points within any given hour. It should be noted that the person is inclined to wake at these time points precisely as they are displayed on the clock, regardless of whether the clock is actually set to the correct time. This means that a person's awakening under the conditions of the experiment is determined not by lighting or biorhythms, as is commonly believed, but by the readings of the clock. The means by which the person is able to see or observe the readings of the hidden clock is unclear, which questions whether mystical psychic means are driving this phenomenon. This study presents the hypothesis that this vision does not occur as direct sensory observation, but possibly through an agent, such as a soul. Significant additional research is needed.

Keywords: circadian rhythms, invisible clock readings, extrasensory perception.

This study was inspired by occasional spontaneous observations. The experimenter became conscious that he often awoke at specific time points, even though there was no obligation for him to wake up at any given time. Upon waking up the clock on his bedside table would reflect one of the ¼ hour marks (00, 15, 30 or 45 min) within the given hour. These observations seemed suspiciously peculiar. It was decided to find answers in existing literature or, alternatively, through experimentation, should existing research fail to provide an explanation for this phenomenon.

It is natural to assume that the observed occurrence is associated with circadian rhythms, which are involved in many biological processes.

Circadian rhythms are biological cycles that control the timings of various processes in living organisms, such as sleep-wake cycles [1,3,10,11]. According to the existing literature, mechanisms that stimulate people to wake up at certain times include both circadian rhythms and light.

Aim

The purpose of this study was to investigate whether mechanisms other than circadian rhythms and light could influence people to wake up at specific times

Method

Experiment 1

An analogue alarm clock was set and placed face-up on a chair next to the experimenter's bed. A cardboard screen was attached to the alarm clock, to cover its face, so that the dial was not visible from the experimenter's point of view. A pencil and paper were also placed on the chair.

The experimenter willed himself to wake up, if possible, in correspondence with the target wake-up times: 00 min, 15 min, 30 min, or 45 min, during any hour, and recorded the actual times at which he awoke. The number of times the experimenter would wake up was unknown and could not be determined in advance. In fact, the experimenter woke up one to ten times a night. It is important to carefully consider the merit of self-suggestion as a waking mechanism, since it is a subjective and poorly controlled factor [6]. If waking

by self-suggestion is ineffective, the results obtained will show a large dispersion.

Before the waking time records were further processed, the times were converted into deviations in minutes (time distances) from the nearest waking time target point. For example, if the time was originally recorded as 4:16 am, it was converted to the time distance +1 min; similarly, a recorded time of 5:28 am was converted to the closest time distance -2 min.

According to the first hypothesis, should the wake-up times be grouped around the mentioned target wake-up times (where the averaged distribution curve reaches a maximum at the target wake-up time), this would indicate that the actual waking times are determined by the target waking times. This means that the experimenter's self-suggestion determines, with some minor or inconsequential degree of error, his time of awakening. Alternatively, the second hypothesis suggests that should these times be evenly distributed (where the averaged distribution curve is flat), it would show that the wake-up times are not related to any of the target wake-up times, and so we must conclude that the self-suggestion of the experimenter does not affect his wake-up times.

Which of these two hypotheses should be accepted, or whether the averaged distribution curve has a maximum or is flat, will be determined by statistical analysis.

Experiment 2

Experiment 2 aimed to clarify the following problem: After completing Experiment 1, it remained unclear whether waking up at these target times was due to the experimenter somehow being able to read the face of the clock behind the screen or because of extremely accurate circadian rhythms. To eliminate this uncertainty in Experiment 2, the researcher's assistant randomly moved the hands of the alarm clock by 7 min (half the distance between the target waking times) forward or backward every evening without informing the experimenter.

If waking up at the targeted times was determined by reading the clock instead of circadian rhythms, then the waking times will be near the target wake-up times

according to the clock. Consequently, the average time interval between each recorded actual time of awakening and the nearest target time of awakening will be approximately the same as in Experiment 1.

If waking up at the target times is determined by circadian rhythms, then the actual waking times should be in accordance with the actual time, and not with the adjusted time as shown on the clock. Additionally, the average time interval between each recorded actual

waking time and the nearest waking target time in Experiment 2 would be approximately 7 min.

Results and statistical analysis

Experiment 1.

Data obtained in Experiment 1, where the hidden alarm clock showed the correct time, are shown in Table 1 and Table 2, where d (minutes) equals the time distance between the nearest target wake-up time and the actual wake-up time.

Table 1.

Data obtained in Experiment 1, where the clock is set to the correct time.

Trial №	d, min												
1	0	11	0	21	-5	31	4	41	2	51	-1	61	1
2	7	12	-3	22	0	32	5	42	-5	52	1	62	0
3	4	13	5	23	1	33	0	43	-5	53	2	63	2
4	-1	14	1	24	1	34	0	44	0	54	0	64	-2
5	5	15	-1	25	1	35	-1	45	1	55	-5	65	-1
6	1	16	3	26	0	36	1	46	4	56	1	66	-2
7	2	17	-2	27	-2	37	1	47	0	57	3	67	2
8	1	18	0	28	2	38	0	48	0	58	-1	68	-2
9	1	19	7	29	7	39	-2	49	2	59	-1		
10	2	20	0	30	0	40	-1	50	1	60	2		

Table 2

Time distance, d, minutes between the actual wake-up time and the nearest target wake-up time	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Number of awakenings between the nearest target wake-up time and the actual wake-up time	4	0	1	5	8	15	14	9	2	3	3	0	3

The data in Table 2 are presented in the Chart 1.

Chart 1. Number of awakenings vs. time distance between the actual wake-up time and the nearest target wake-up time in experiment 1. Moving average trendline.

Time distance (d, min) between the actual wake-up time and the nearest target wake-up time

Both Table 2 and Chart 1 show that the data distribution is not uniform but looks like a normal distribution, i.e., this distribution has a maximum. Whether this distribution is not flat, but indeed normal, will be determined through statistical analysis using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test of Normality, (<https://www.socscistatistics.com/tests/kolmogorov/default.aspx>). This test gave the following conclusion: "Your data does not differ significantly from that which is normally distributed."

Therefore, the statistical analysis of the time distances shows that they are grouped around the target

wake-up times (averaged distribution curve has a maximum at the target wake-up time). This indicates that the actual wake-up times are determined by these target wake-up times, that is, the self-suggestion of the experimenter determines, with some minor or inconsequential degree of error, the time of waking up.

Experiment 2.

Data obtained in Experiment 2 (37 records total), when the hidden alarm clock showed the wrong time, are given in Table 3, where d (min) is the time distance between the nearest target wake-up time and the actual wake-up time.

Table 3.

Data obtained in Experiment 2

Trial №	d, min						
1	0	11	1	21	2	31	5
2	1	12	-3	22	-1	32	3
3	-5	13	3	23	-1	33	-1
4	-2	14	3	24	2	34	0
5	0	15	-3	25	1	35	5
6	2	16	-3	26	-6	36	-5
7	-2	17	-2	27	-4	37	0
8	-2	18	2	28	1		
9	0	19	-4	29	-5		
10	-5	20	1	30	-5		

In this experiment, while the clock shows the wrong time (shifted by 7 min), the time interval between each recorded actual time of awakening and the nearest target wake-up time is 0.73 ± 3.0 min. In Experiment 1, during which the clock showed the correct time, this time interval was 0.63 ± 2.6 min. These results are remarkably close to those in Experiment 1. Therefore, as described above, we must conclude that the experimenter's ability to wake up at the target waking times, is a result of his ability to read the clock while sleeping instead of circadian rhythms.

Discussion

The results obtained in Experiments 1 and 2 indicate that the time of awakening is not determined by circadian rhythms, but by the time displayed on the alarm clock. If the waking time was determined by circadian rhythms, the time distance between each recorded time after awakening and the time of the nearest waking target point would be approximately 7 min, in Experiment 2.

We found that the average time distance between each actual wake-up time and the nearest target wake-up time was less than 1 min (0.63 ± 2.6 min. and 0.73 ± 3.0 min). It is unclear how a sleeping person is able to track the time displayed on the clock. The underlying cause of this phenomenon is unknown and warrants further research. For example, one can hypothesize an association between our results and the phenomenon of extrasensory perception, arguably clairvoyance, or in a special case, remote viewing [2, 4, 7-9]. However, in these hypotheses it cannot be ruled out that an otherworldly agent, such as a soul, may be involved in this mysterious phenomenon of extrasensory perception.

The purpose of this article is to inform about a previously unknown phenomenon, the ability of a person to see the clock face invisible to him. The mechanism

of this phenomenon is unknown, and we conditionally call it extrasensory perception, but this name does not reflect any specific, scientifically proven mechanism. Further detailed study of this phenomenon, for example, dependance from the distance between the researcher and the clock, the possibility of its shielding by metal and other shields, is beyond the scope of this study.

Our study was conducted in the dark, while remote viewing studies are usually conducted in a lit environment. A recent study by Krippner et al. [5] found that dark condition performance heeded more substantial results, but the difference was not statistically significant. This conclusion is in favour of the assumption that the observed phenomenon may be a type of remote viewing.

The experimenter recently encountered a similar phenomenon in a lit environment. He experienced a remote viewing incident, not in a dream, but in reality. After this study was concluded, the experimenter began to notice that he suspiciously often sees an "exact" time, such as the time target points set in this study, when he looks at his watch. Such occasional observations are of course, unreliable. However, on the evening of December 18, 2020, four such observations happened in succession, the results of which deserve attention. This date should be noted for potential future studies in correlation with, for example, the phases of the moon.

This observation occurred as follows: The researcher noted that it was exactly 9:00 PM when he concluded his work for the day. Subsequently, he spent some time watching television, YouTube, and listening to music before looking at his watch again at exactly 9:30 PM. He looked at his watch again at 9:45 PM and 10:00 PM precisely. This remarkable coincidence where he had the urge to look at his watch at precise

intervals reflects the probability of remote observation, where the agent could be a soul. This hypothesis, although weak, seems to have some advantage over the hypothesis that uses the vague concept of extrasensory perception without the involvement of any intermediary, agent.

Conclusion

The investigated phenomenon is not caused by circadian rhythms, but by the ability of a sleeping person to read the time shown by an alarm clock, even when it is hidden from sight. This phenomenon is probably caused by some unclear type of extrasensory perception, arguably by remote viewing. More research is needed to investigate the nature of this phenomenon.

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P.S. Currently, the author is designing an electronic device to further study the described phenomenon. Researchers who wish to collaborate in the study can write to simonbas@tpg.com.au

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